

2 poems by Iuliana Pasca

In the middle of myself

I dance around the sun all night
with legs of rays
I break the gates of hell
and slip my glow into its depths
to fill the void of non-existence.

The light does not belong to me
I am the emptiness around it,
the vacuum of darkness
and this luminescence
is a temporary reflection
on the fire burning
under my feet.

The fall

Hysterical screams echo in my mind, the past
pierces me like an iron maiden, convulsive pain
grinds in temples,

I try to sleep, but fear grins from the
bones marrow.

I tremble, I go mad, and fall into the
abyss...

Unconscious,

I join the gloomy desires like
pieces of rancid meat

detaching from an unborn embryo –
a nameless and meaningless non-being.

Invisible demons come out of oblivion and
devour the corpse of the spirit accompanying the
fall
into myself.

Bio

Iuliana Pasca, poet, translator, and photographer from Romania, studied Romanian – Chinese at Babes-Bolyai University and at Zhejiang University. She collaborates with literary magazines from Romania and oversees, including the well-known Ithaca Foundation’s Project Poetry Without Borders.